

Graviton instability and graviton condensation

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Abstract

When multiple real gravitons are present, the quantum gravitational effect, caused by the exchange of virtual gravitons among them, leads to instability in the real gravitons. As a result of this instability, the condensation of real gravitons occurs. For a single isolated real graviton, which is not a bound state of multiple gravitons, the quantum gravitational effect discussed in this paper does not occur, and the classical limit of gravity is correctly reproduced as a soft limit. The mean-field analysis method is used to analyze the graviton condensate. Applications of graviton condensation to the atomic nucleus and the confinement of quarks and gluons are also discussed.

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1 Introduction

We clarify a novel phenomenon that occurs when there is more than one real graviton, and we analyze the properties of this phenomenon. In discussing this subject, there are two main themes in this work:

- When more than one real graviton exists, we find that they exhibit an instability. We clarify and emphasize that, as a consequence of the instability, the condensation of real gravitons occurs when multiple gravitons are present.
- Applying the result of this first theme to the nucleus of an atom, and considering the quark-gluon plasma, we suggest that a previously unnoticed structure may exist in the nucleus.

When more than one real graviton exists, they exchange virtual gravitons among themselves, resulting in each real graviton generating a Kerr black hole geometry [1] around itself, as discussed in [2]. Owing to this mechanism, the presence of multiple real gravitons leads to instability. If a single isolated real graviton is considered, not a bound state of gravitons, the quantum gravitational effect discussed in this paper does not occur, and the classical limit of gravity is correctly reproduced as a soft limit.

Utilizing the instability and performing mean-field analysis, we demonstrate that when there is more than one real graviton, they condense. The mean-field analysis method was used in constructing the Bardeen–Cooper–Schrieffer theory [3, 4], which provides a theoretical microscopic model of superconductivity and describes the Cooper instability [5] as the primary cause of superconductivity.

In actual phenomena, a large number of real gravitons are likely to condense; therefore, a statistical treatment of the phenomenon is expected to be an effective approach, and the application of mean-field analysis is considered to provide a good approximation.

This aspect corresponds to the first of the two aforementioned themes, which we will discuss further in Sections 2 and 4.

The instability of gravitons is discussed in Section 2. First, we consider the situation where a real graviton is confined in a Kerr black hole of classical scale and analyze the physical consequences. Next, we examine the case where a real graviton is confined in a Planck-sized Kerr black hole. Based on these discussions, we then argue that when two (or more) real gravitons are present, the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons causes the geometry around each real graviton to follow the Kerr metric [2]. This implies that when multiple real gravitons are present, each real graviton becomes a composite object.

When the cosmic censorship conjecture [6] is considered, the Kerr geometry formed around each real graviton creates a horizon, which imposes a constraint on the mass parameter of the Kerr black hole geometry surrounding each real graviton, yielding a non-zero, Planck-mass scale lower bound. As a result of the Kerr black hole with the Planck-mass scale mass parameter formed around each graviton, gravitons attract one another. Owing to this mechanism, when multiple real gravitons exist, the negative attractive potential energy is present, leading to instability and the condensation of real gravitons.

The Feynman graphs, representing the bound state formed by real gravitons as discussed in Section 2.3, are described in Section 2.4. In this work, we developed a description using Planck-scale-sized Kerr black holes. From a quantum physical perspective, it is necessary to justify the assumption of this physical notion's existence. In this section, we provide such a justification using Feynman graphs. Another important aspect to discuss is the use of the Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole picture to describe the quantum gravitational effect of real graviton condensation. This description raises the possibility that a sufficiently small neighborhood in spacetime cannot be approximated by flat Minkowski spacetime, as the Planck-scale geometry does not physically allow for the concept of a "sufficiently small neighborhood." If this were to occur, the inability to define a small neighborhood around a point in the geometry would contradict the equivalence principle. This issue will also be addressed in this section.

To be precise, we found in Section 2.4 that the phenomenon of real gravitons joining together due to the quantum gravitational effect originates from the virtual graviton propagator behaving as it would in a curved spacetime due to a nonperturbative effect of gravity. The Planck-scale sized Kerr black hole picture is used in this study to compute this non-perturbative effect. In reality, the effect of Planck-scale-sized curved spacetime geometry is incorporated into this virtual process, ensuring that the real physics does not contradict the equivalence principle.

In Section 3, we compute the interaction between two real gravitons through virtual graviton exchange, including the nonperturbative effects from the leaf Feynman diagram introduced in Section 2.4. Our quantum field-theoretic computation, using the Feynman diagrams, confirmed that an attractive potential indeed arises in the interaction, and as a result, the two

real gravitons are strongly bound together. This provides confirmation of the discussions presented in Section 2, thus justifying the assertions made therein.

A mean-field analysis is applied to the graviton condensate in Section 4. We apply a mean-field analysis to the graviton condensate and estimate the spacing between real gravitons in the condensate.

A theoretical model of quark-gluon plasma, produced the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC), as a gas of quarks and gluons confined within a film of graviton condensate, was proposed in [7]. As pointed out in [7], this model explains the very low viscosity of the quark-gluon plasma observed in experiments.

However, when comparing the energy scales of graviton and quantum chromodynamics (QCD), the energy involved in the RHIC experiment that produced the quark-gluon plasma was far too low to generate gravitons. This leads us to postulate that there exists a film of graviton condensate surrounding the nucleus of an atom. Specifically, we propose an atomic model in which the atom is composed not only of a nucleus and electrons bound to it, but also includes a graviton film as part of its structure, covering the nucleus. This corresponds to the second theme, which will be discussed in Section 5.

We also explore potential connections between gravitational and QCD phenomena. The graviton film may be responsible for the confinement of quarks and gluons.

We state our concluding remarks in Section 6.

In this paper, we consider a two-dimensional surface composed of gravitons, resulting from graviton condensation, which we refer to as a “graviton film.” We examine situations where the size of this graviton film is much larger than the Planck length—for example, where the size of the film is comparable to that of the nucleus of an atom. Each graviton within the film is expected to move throughout the entire film, so the position uncertainty of each graviton is on the order of the size of the graviton film. This characteristic ensures that the graviton condensate forming the film does not dissipate.

The hypothesis that a virtual graviton with a momentum surpassing a threshold value generates a Kerr black hole geometry leads to a consistent four-dimensional quantum gravitational theory, where elementary particles are treated as point particles [2]. We take this standpoint in this paper: spacetime dimensions are four, and elementary particles are treated as point particles. Nonperturbative quantum gravitational aspects of graviton are specifically discussed in this study. Quantum gravity was perturbatively analyzed, for example, in [8, 9, 10, 11, 12].

2 Quantum gravitational effect and the bound state of real gravitons

2.1 Our postulate

As an initial step, we begin by considering the situation where a real graviton is confined in a Kerr black hole of a classical scale, i.e., not a Planck scale. Such a situation corresponds to

the regime of Einstein's general theory of relativity, where the quantum effect is insignificant.

When the Kerr metric [1] is expressed in terms of the Boyer–Lindquist coordinates (t, r, θ, ϕ) [13], the Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) in the 3-space are represented by the Boyer–Lindquist coordinates in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \sqrt{r^2 + a^2} \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ y &= \sqrt{r^2 + a^2} \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ z &= r \cos \theta, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where a represents the quantity J/M ,

$$a = \frac{J}{Mc}. \quad (2)$$

M and J represent the mass parameter and the angular momentum of the Kerr black hole, respectively.

The ring singularity inside the horizon of the Kerr metric is expressed as the boundary ring of a disk,

$$r = 0, \quad \theta = \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (3)$$

in the Boyer–Lindquist coordinates.

If the configuration of the confined real graviton does not break the axial symmetry of the Kerr black hole, owing to the no-hair theorem, the resulting geometry after the real graviton is confined inside the Kerr black hole must be the Kerr black hole. This is possible, for example, when the graviton is located at $r = 0, \theta = 0$ in the Boyer–Lindquist coordinates, which corresponds to the point $x = y = z = 0$ in the 3-space in the Cartesian coordinates. When the angular momentum of the Kerr metric before it confines the graviton is denoted as J , because the graviton has spin 2, the angular momentum of the resulting Kerr black hole after it confines the graviton is $J + 2\hbar$.

Particularly, when the Kerr black hole initially does not possess angular momentum, i.e., when $J = 0$, which corresponds to the special case where the Kerr black hole is initially the Schwarzschild black hole [14], the Kerr black hole after it confines the real graviton has angular momentum $2\hbar$.

Next, we consider the Planck-sized Kerr black hole. In this case, the quantum gravitational effect is expected to become significant. We hypothesize that the description we just provided still applies to this regime. Namely, we postulate that at the Planck-size scale, the Kerr black hole is described by the following metric:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= - \left(1 - \frac{2GM r}{c^2 [r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta]} \right) (cdt)^2 - \frac{4GM r a \sin^2 \theta}{c^2 [r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta]} (cdt)d\phi + \frac{r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{r^2 + a^2 - \frac{2GM}{c^2} r} dr^2 \\ &+ (r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta) d\theta^2 + \left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{2GM r a^2}{c^2 [r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta]} \sin^2 \theta \right) \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the coordinates (t, r, θ, ϕ) are used to denote Boyer–Lindquist coordinates [13], and the resulting geometry after it confines a real graviton is the Kerr black hole with angular momentum $J + 2\hbar$. Here, J represents the angular momentum of the Kerr black hole before it confines the graviton.

2.2 Virtual graviton and the Kerr metric around a real graviton

Taking the quantum nature of gravity into consideration, when two (or more) gravitons are present, they exchange virtual gravitons due to quantum gravitational effects. Applying the discussion given in [2] to this situation reveals that the geometry around each of the two gravitons is described by the Kerr metric.

If a horizon does not form in the Kerr metric around a real graviton generated by virtual gravitons, it results in the appearance of a naked singularity, violating the cosmic censorship conjecture [6]. From this reasoning, we conclude that the horizon indeed forms in the Kerr metric around the real graviton, resulting in the Kerr black hole geometry.

According to Hawking radiation, one might consider that the resulting Kerr black hole around the graviton can undergo an evaporating process; however, gravitons continuously exchange virtual gravitons, preventing the Planck-sized Kerr black hole around the real graviton from evaporating. Given this, we can conclude that the Kerr black hole around the graviton exists stably.

A graviton does not carry an electric charge or a magnetic charge, but it has spin angular momentum. Therefore, applying the no-hair theorem of black holes to the black hole formed around the real graviton also provides another confirmation that the resulting geometry must be the Kerr black hole.

From these discussions, we deduce that, as a quantum gravitational effect, when two real gravitons are present, the Planck-scale Kerr black hole forms around each of the two gravitons, resulting in a situation where each of the two real gravitons is confined within its own Kerr black hole. Since virtual gravitons are undetectable, they do not contribute to the formed Kerr black holes, and the angular momentum of the Kerr black hole that confines a real graviton purely originates from the spin angular momentum of the real graviton it confines.

Thus, we deduce that the Kerr black hole formed around a real graviton has angular momentum $J = 2\hbar$. The formation of the horizon in the Kerr metric, making it a black hole geometry, requires the following condition to be met:

$$2\hbar \leq \frac{M^2 G}{c}. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the mass parameter M of the Kerr black hole confining the real graviton has the following lower bound:

$$M \geq \sqrt{\frac{2\hbar c}{G}} = \sqrt{2}m_P, \quad (6)$$

where m_P represents the Planck mass. This relation implies that the mass parameter of the Kerr black hole confining the real graviton is on the order of the Planck mass. The radius r_+

of the horizon of the Kerr black hole under discussion is given by:

$$r_+ = \frac{GM}{c^2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{GM}{c^2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2\hbar}{Mc}\right)^2}; \quad (7)$$

therefore, the radius r_+ satisfies the relations

$$\frac{2GM}{c^2} > r_+ \geq \frac{GM}{c^2}. \quad (8)$$

Given this, since we found that the mass parameter M of the Kerr black hole under discussion is on the order of the Planck scale, the radius r_+ is on the order of the Planck length, i.e., the Kerr black hole confining the real graviton is Planck-scale sized.

A real graviton with a geometric structure confined within a Planck-scale sized Kerr black hole can be viewed as a sort of a composite object.

This composite object structure of a real graviton, confined within the Kerr black hole, carries the Planck-scale mass parameter of the spacetime structure (although the graviton itself is massless). This structure is clearly distinct from a structureless graviton, where the metric around it is flat and does not carry such a nontrivial mass parameter.

2.3 Bound state of two gravitons and instability

We previously discussed that when two real gravitons are present, due to the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons, a Planck-scale sized Kerr black hole forms around each real graviton. This results in each real graviton becoming a sort of composite object confined within its own Kerr black hole. We also found that the mass parameters of these Kerr black holes are on the order of the Planck mass m_P , and they satisfy the lower bound (6).

As a result of the Kerr black hole with a mass parameter on the order of the Planck mass m_P formed around each of the two gravitons, the gravitons attract each other. The total energy of this system is not simply the sum of the energies of the two gravitons; the negative potential energy arising from the attractive potential is added to the sum of the graviton energies. Due to the presence of the negative potential energy, the total energy of the system of two real gravitons is strictly less than the sum of the two graviton energies.

Similarly, when n gravitons are present, where n represents an integer larger than or equal to two, the total energy of the system of n gravitons is strictly less than the sum of the energies of n gravitons, since the negative attractive potential energy is present.

As a consequence of this mechanism, the system of two real gravitons exhibits instability, and the two gravitons can form a bound state. Applying this argument to a system of multiple gravitons reveals that the system possesses instability, suggesting a tendency to form an aggregated body.

These arguments suggest the possibility that a large number of real gravitons could condense to form an aggregated body. In the next section, we utilize the mean-field analysis to examine this structure.

Figure 1: A Feynman diagram representing a virtual graviton propagator branching into n_1 branches (with red nodes) and another virtual graviton propagator starting with n_2 branches (with blue nodes) that converge into a single virtual graviton propagator. The case where $n_1 = n_2 = 7$ is shown.

2.4 Feynman diagram representing the bound state of two gravitons

In Section 2.2, we discussed that when two (or more) real gravitons are present, the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons causes each real graviton to generate the Kerr metric around it, forming a Planck-sized Kerr black hole. We argued in Section 2.3 that, as a result, multiple real gravitons exhibit instability and form a bound state as an aggregated body.

However, a virtual graviton is a transient effect, while the metric is a static concept. There is a conceptual “gap” in how the exchange of virtual gravitons results in changes in the metric. To address this ambiguity, we describe the Feynman graph, which represents the bound state of two real gravitons formed through the exchange of virtual gravitons.

Due to the nonlinearity of gravity, an n -graviton vertex exists for any natural number $n \geq 3$. Therefore, a virtual graviton propagator can branch into any number of branches, and this branching can continue recursively any number of times. These higher graviton vertices are suppressed at low energies, and their contributions do not significantly affect physical phenomena. However, at the Planck scale, these contributions become dominant, and their effects become apparent in the physical phenomena.

The following Feynman diagram essentially corresponds to two real gravitons forming a bound state through the exchange of virtual gravitons: Since gravity is nonlinear, a virtual graviton propagator can branch into n branches for any natural number $n \geq 2$. (When $n = 1$, there is no branching, which simply corresponds to a virtual graviton propagator.) We consider two virtual graviton propagators: one branching into n_1 branches and the other beginning with n_2 branches that converge into a single virtual graviton propagator (Figure 1).

As shown in Figure 1, there are n_1 red nodes and n_2 blue nodes. We adopt a convention in which pairs of red and blue nodes are connected by virtual graviton propagators, where successive branchings are allowed for virtual graviton propagators linking a red node to a blue node. The amplitude is given as the sum over all possible such connections via virtual graviton propagators. We use Figure 1 to represent this amplitude. n_1 and n_2 take values in the natural numbers, but the cases $n_1 = 1$ and $n_2 = 1$ correspond to no branching. Therefore, we only consider cases where $n_1, n_2 \geq 2$.

The Feynman graph in Figure 1 resembles a leaf rather than a tree. For this reason, we refer to this graph as a *leaf diagram* in this study.

The Feynman graphs with the leaf diagrams represent two real gravitons forming a bound state through the exchange of virtual gravitons. Therefore, these Feynman diagrams should correspond to the bound state formed by two real gravitons, as described in Section 2.3. Although these graphs do not allow for a perturbative computation, we expect them to reproduce the classical Kerr solution. Due to the inability to perform a perturbative evaluation of the graphs, we used the depiction of Planck-scale-sized Kerr black holes, as described by the classical Kerr metric, to model the bound state of real gravitons resulting from the quantum gravitational effect.

We now discuss the modification effects of corrections arising from the Feynman leaf diagrams on the virtual graviton propagator. There are n -graviton vertices for any $n \geq 3$, and owing to the presence of the factor $\sqrt{-g}$ in the Einstein–Hilbert action, there is no upper bound on the natural number n for which an n -graviton vertex exists. By expanding the Einstein–Hilbert action in terms of the graviton field, one obtains the corresponding Feynman diagrams, where the leaf diagram corresponds to higher-order corrections. This analysis suggests that the sum of the leaf diagrams (together with a single-line virtual graviton propagator) yields the virtual graviton propagator in a curved spacetime.

Considering the interaction between two real gravitons, the axial symmetry and the no-hair theorem suggest that the Kerr metric is a plausible choice for the background spacetime of the virtual graviton propagator. As previously mentioned, the mass parameter M of the Kerr metric in this study is on the order of the Planck mass, $M \sim \sqrt{2}m_P$.

An argument analogous to the one we previously presented applies to the graviton self-energy. The leaf virtual graviton propagator, attached to two external graviton lines, produces the graviton self-energy diagram that incorporates nonperturbative effects (Figure 2). Applying the argument we previously made, the leaf Feynman diagram results in the graviton propagator taking the form it would have in the Kerr spacetime background, connected to two external graviton lines.

The physical interpretation of the nonperturbative effect arising from the graviton self-energy graph described above is as follows: the leaf diagram modifies the virtual graviton propagator to that in the Kerr spacetime background. This corresponds to the quantum field-theoretic description of the semi-classical picture, wherein a graviton, (perturbatively) massless due to diffeomorphism invariance, is confined within a Kerr black hole. Based on physical reasoning, the cutoff scale is on the order of the Planck mass, m_P ; therefore, the mass parameter of the Kerr black hole is also on the order of the Planck mass. This effect

Figure 2: The leaf diagram of a virtual graviton propagator yields a nonperturbative self-energy correction to the graviton. A semi-classical interpretation is that a real graviton is confined within a Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole, resulting in a composite object with a mass on the order of the Planck mass, m_P .

becomes significant only at high energies. As mentioned in the previous argument, we set the mass parameter M to $\sqrt{2}m_P$: $M \sim \sqrt{2}m_P$. The composite-object description of a real graviton confined within a Planck-sized Kerr black hole was provided in Section 2.2. The description here offers a more refined and precise quantum field-theoretic version of the semi-classical description given in Section 2.2. This argument validates the earlier semi-classical interpretation.

We note that the nonperturbative correction from the leaf diagram becomes significant only at the Planck scale—that is, at Planck-scale energies, or equivalently, Planck-length scales. This effect cannot be observed effectively at distances from a real graviton that exceed the Planck-length scale. It becomes significant only when real gravitons are separated by a distance on the order of the Planck length, l_P .

Given this reasoning, real gravitons separated by a distance on the order of the Planck length are no longer simply massless spin-2 particles; they must be treated as composite objects with Planck-scale masses for computational purposes.

Based on the leaf Feynman diagram description provided earlier, we now demonstrate that real gravitons separated by distances on the order of the Planck length form a bound state, resulting in real graviton condensation. The demonstration that we present below is qualitative. Computational and quantitative aspects will be provided in detail to validate our assertion in Section 3.

When two (or more) real gravitons are located within a distance on the order of the Planck length, the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons causes the virtual graviton propagator to transition to a propagator in the Kerr spacetime. As a result of this effect, along with the nonperturbative contribution from the leaf diagram representing

graviton self-energy renormalization ¹, each of the two real gravitons becomes a composite-like object carrying a Planck-scale mass of $\sqrt{2}m_P$, and they become bound together.

At this point, we offer a remark: the radius of the horizon in the Kerr black hole r_+ is on the order of the Planck length l_P , i.e., $r_+ = \frac{GM}{c^2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{GM}{c^2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2\hbar}{Mc}\right)^2} \sim \sqrt{2}l_P$, when $M \sim \sqrt{2}l_P$. We focus on the distance scale between two real gravitons being on the order of the Planck length, as the graviton condensation mechanism is expected to become effective at this scale. Consequently, the horizon radius of the background metric and the distance scale between two real gravitons are of the same order. As a result, the usual near-horizon approximation does not apply to the model discussed in this study. Additionally, because the horizon radius of the model under discussion is on the order of the Planck length, discussing a distance to the horizon much shorter than the horizon radius lacks physical meaning. Length scales much shorter than the Planck length do not physically exist. This means that making a near-horizon approximation is physically impossible in the model under discussion, and the virtual graviton propagator does not reduce to that in flat Minkowski spacetime.

This argument, based on leaf Feynman diagrams, justifies the description provided in previous sections, where each real graviton forms its own Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole due to the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons, and are bound together.

Our discussion suggests that this phenomenon is characteristic of gravitons that yield a leaf Feynman diagram as higher-order corrections.

The previously described Feynman graphs provide an accurate depiction of what actually occurs in physics. We used the classical picture of the Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole for computations, as performing the nonperturbative computation of adding the leaf Feynman diagrams is considerably challenging. In contrast to a curved spacetime with a size sufficiently larger than the Planck scale, the Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole raises the possibility that a point in this geometry does not have a neighborhood that can be approximated by flat Minkowski spacetime. This is because distances shorter than the Planck length do not have physical meaning. Therefore, the use of the Planck-scale-sized Kerr black hole picture has the potential to contradict the equivalence principle.

However, as we clarified in this section, what happens in physics, more precisely, is that a virtual graviton propagator behaves as it would in curved spacetime owing to the nonperturbative effect of the leaf Feynman diagrams. Real gravitons are joined as a result of this nonperturbative effect, which originates from a virtual process. We emphasize that the actual physics does not contradict the equivalence principle.

As previously discussed, the condensation phenomenon of real gravitons can be accurately understood only as a result of virtual processes described by the leaf Feynman diagrams.

Considering the equivalence principle along with diffeomorphism invariance, the background metric in the virtual graviton process essentially remains as the only aspect potentially affected by the nonperturbative effects arising from graviton renormalization. The nonperturbative effects from the leaf diagrams inevitably result in the description we have just provided.

¹An ultraviolet-finite four-dimensional quantum gravitational theory can be consistently constructed [2].

3 Computational method for the Feynman diagram of bound states of real gravitons

We introduce a computational scheme to evaluate the potential of the bound state formed by two real gravitons separated by distances on the order of the Planck length. As a consequence of our computational results, we confirm that two real gravitons are strongly joined, as discussed in Section 2.

As stated in Section 2.4 using the leaf Feynman diagrams and including nonperturbative effects, the virtual graviton propagator transitions to behave as it would in a curved spacetime background. Based on the reasoning that the curved background spacetime is expected to be the Kerr spacetime—owing to self-energy renormalization incorporating nonperturbative effects—a real graviton becomes a composite-like object with effective mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$. This effect is significant only within distances on the order of the Planck length from the real graviton. The phenomenon of two real gravitons joining together to form a bound state occurs only at separations of this length scale. That the effective mass of a real graviton, when it becomes a composite object, is on the order of the Planck mass m_P is plausible, given that quantum gravitational effects become significant only at the Planck scale.

While we argued that the curved spacetime background of the propagator—into which the virtual graviton propagator transitions while incorporating nonperturbative effects of the leaf Feynman diagrams—would be the Kerr spacetime, we used this specific metric only to derive that the real graviton becomes a composite object acquiring the effective mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$. The discussions in this section do not depend on the specific metric form of the curved spacetime background of the virtual process, except for the property that the real graviton effectively becomes a composite-like object with effective mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$. We develop a computational method in a general curved spacetime background in this sense, without relying on the details of the background metric of the virtual process.

Physically, this fact can be interpreted as follows: when a gas of quarks and gluons is confined within an aggregated film composed of condensed real gravitons, although the geometric shape of the graviton film would change significantly due to the pressure of the quark-gluon gas, the computational results deduced in this section still apply to the graviton film. The fact that the computational scheme in this section is, in essence, independent of the metric details of the background spacetime of the virtual process allows for perturbations from the specified Kerr metric.

When the virtual graviton propagator transitions to one in a curved spacetime background, the transformation process between position-space representation and momentum-space representation via Fourier transform becomes nontrivial. However, it seems reasonable to assume that replacing the flat Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ in the virtual graviton propagator in the Minkowski spacetime background with $g_{\mu\nu}$ in the curved spacetime background—where $g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the curved spacetime background metric—provides an appropriate description. Therefore, the virtual graviton propagator $P_{\mu\nu,\rho\sigma}$ in the curved spacetime background,

Figure 3: A diagram of two real gravitons scattering through the exchange of a virtual graviton, including the nonperturbative effects arising from the leaf Feynman diagrams, is displayed. The nonperturbative effect causes the virtual graviton propagator to transition to a propagator in a curved spacetime background, and the real gravitons become composite-like objects with an effective mass on the order of the Planck mass owing to the nonperturbative effect.

incorporating the nonperturbative effects of the leaf Feynman diagram, is given by:

$$P_{\mu\nu,\rho\sigma} = \frac{i}{2q^2} (g_{\mu\rho}g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\nu\rho} - g_{\mu\nu}g_{\rho\sigma}), \quad (9)$$

where q represents the transferred momentum.

Now, at leading order, we compute the potential arising from virtual graviton exchange between two real gravitons separated by distances on the order of the Planck length, including nonperturbative effects. As discussed earlier, the two real gravitons become composite objects of mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$ owing to self-energy renormalization. For notational simplicity, we denote this mass by m , i.e., $m := \sqrt{2}m_P$.

We label the two real gravitons as 1 and 2 and use the labels a_1 and b_1 for the incoming state of real graviton 1. Similarly, we use a_2 and b_2 for the incoming state of real graviton 2. For the outgoing states, we use the labels c_1 and d_1 for graviton 1 and c_2 and d_2 for graviton 2. The indices of the virtual graviton propagator representing virtual graviton exchange on the graviton 1 side are labeled μ and ν , while on the graviton 2 side, they are labeled ρ and σ .

We denote the momenta of the incoming and outgoing states of real graviton 1 by k_1^μ and $k_1'^\mu$, respectively. The momenta of the incoming and outgoing states of real graviton 2 are denoted by k_2^μ and $k_2'^\mu$, respectively. The transferred momentum from real graviton 1 to real graviton 2 via a virtual graviton propagator is denoted by q . Therefore, we have $k_1' = k_1 - q$, and $k_2' = k_2 + q$. The scattering process of real gravitons 1 and 2 through virtual graviton exchange is illustrated in Figure 3.

Since real gravitons 1 and 2 are composite objects with effective mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$, we have ²

$$k_{1\mu}k_1^\mu = k'_{1\mu}k_1'^\mu = k_{2\rho}k_2^\rho = k'_{2\rho}k_2'^\rho = m^2 = 2m_P^2. \quad (10)$$

Having introduced the notational conventions, we now compute the amplitude of the scattering process of the two real gravitons 1 and 2 through the exchange of a virtual graviton. Since both real gravitons possess effective mass m , we consider the limit in which they are both at rest. In this limit, we have $k_1^\mu \sim k_1'^\mu$, $k_2^\mu \sim k_2'^\mu$, and $q \sim 0$.

In this limit, the Feynman rules for the two three-point graviton vertices in the scattering process, as depicted in Figure 3, simplify. We denote the three-point graviton vertex, which consists of three graviton lines, with one line carrying the indices of the incoming state a and b , one line carrying the indices of the outgoing state c and d , and one line carrying the indices of the virtual graviton propagator μ and ν , by $V_{ab,cd,\mu\nu}$.

From a symmetry argument, together with diffeomorphism invariance, one finds that in the stationary limit $q \sim 0$, the expression for the three-graviton vertex is proportional to $(k^\mu k^\nu + k'^\mu k'^\nu)$. Thus, in the limit where the two real gravitons are stationary ($q \sim 0$), the three-point graviton vertex $V_{ab,cd,\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$V_{ab,cd,\mu\nu} = \frac{i\sqrt{32\pi G}}{2} (k^\mu k^\nu + k'^\mu k'^\nu) Q_{ab,cd}, \quad (11)$$

where we introduced the notation $Q_{ab,cd} := \frac{1}{2} (\eta_{ac}\eta_{bd} + \eta_{ad}\eta_{bc} - \eta_{ab}\eta_{cd})$.

Now, we are ready to evaluate the amplitude \mathcal{M} of the scattering process of two real gravitons through virtual graviton exchange, including the nonperturbative effects (in the stationary limit, where the two real gravitons are at rest). From the derived Feynman rules, incorporating the nonperturbative effects arising from the leaf Feynman diagrams, the amplitude is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i\mathcal{M} &= \left(\frac{i\sqrt{32\pi G}}{2} \right)^2 (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) \frac{i}{2q^2} (g_{\mu\rho}g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\nu\rho} - g_{\mu\nu}g_{\rho\sigma}) \\ &\quad \times (k_2^\rho k_2^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2'^\sigma) Q_{a_1b_1,c_1d_1} Q_{a_2b_2,c_2d_2}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

First, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} &(k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) (g_{\mu\rho}g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\nu\rho} - g_{\mu\nu}g_{\rho\sigma}) (k_2^\rho k_2^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2'^\sigma) \\ &= 2 \left((k_1 \cdot k_2)^2 + (k_1' \cdot k_2)^2 + (k_1 \cdot k_2')^2 + (k_1' \cdot k_2')^2 \right) - (k_1^2 + k_1'^2) (k_2^2 + k_2'^2). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We have $k_1^2 = k_1'^2 = k_2^2 = k_2'^2 = m^2$. In the stationary limit, where the two real gravitons are at rest, we have $k_1 \cdot k_2 = k_1' \cdot k_2 = k_1 \cdot k_2' = k_1' \cdot k_2' = m^2$. Therefore, quantity (13) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} &2 \left((m^2)^2 + (m^2)^2 + (m^2)^2 + (m^2)^2 \right) - 2m^2 \cdot 2m^2 \\ &= 8m^4 - 4m^4 = 4m^4. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

²We used the metric signature convention of $(-, +, +, +)$ in Section 2.1. However, to align with the convention frequently used in quantum field theory, we adopt the $(+, -, -, -)$ convention for the spacetime metric in this section.

Thus, we finally obtain:

$$\mathcal{M} = -\frac{32\pi G}{8q^2} 4m^4 = \frac{4\pi G m^2}{|\mathbf{q}|^2} \cdot (2m)^2. \quad (15)$$

After applying the Fourier transform to this expression (multiplied by $\frac{1}{4m^2}$ for normalization, which applies to the stationary limit where both real gravitons are at rest), we eventually arrive at the potential of two real gravitons at leading order, including the nonperturbative effects of the leaf Feynman diagrams, as follows:

$$\boxed{V = -G \frac{m^2}{r} = -G \frac{2m_P^2}{r}.} \quad (16)$$

r represents the distance between the two real gravitons. This computational result demonstrates that two real gravitons are strongly bound together, justifying the discussions presented in Section 2. Note that since the separation of the two real gravitons under discussion is on the order of the Planck length, the deduced potential is on the order of the Planck energy, $V = -G \frac{2m_P^2}{r} \sim -G \frac{2m_P^2}{l_P} = -2E_P$, where E_P represents the Planck energy. From the deduced expression (16), we learn that the leading-order contribution to the potential of two real gravitons through exchange of virtual gravitons does not depend on the details of the background metric $g_{\mu\nu}$. In this sense, **the result is both general and universal. This fact implies that when real gravitons condense owing to the instability to form an aggregated body, perturbations (such as those from the surroundings) do not affect the integrity of this graviton condensation, and the condensed aggregated body exists stably.**

4 Graviton condensation and mean-field analysis

We clarified the instability of real gravitons and highlighted the possibility that a large number of gravitons can aggregate to form a collective body in the previous section. In this section, we analyze the properties of this aggregated body of gravitons using the mean-field approximation.

We consider the situation where real gravitons aggregate to form a collective body, with gravitons equally spaced by distance d . Real gravitons exchange virtual gravitons, and owing to this quantum gravitational effect, a Planck-scale sized Kerr black hole with a mass parameter on the order of the Planck mass m_P forms around each real graviton, as discussed in the previous section. This mechanism causes real gravitons to be strongly bound to one another.

As the real gravitons, confined within their own Kerr black holes, exchange virtual gravitons, the spacetime structure around each real graviton is expected to fluctuate. We use the mean-field approximation of this fluctuation to conduct the mean-field analysis. Through exchanging virtual gravitons, the positive and negative variations in the angular momentum of the Kerr black hole formed around a real graviton must occur with equal probabilities.

Therefore, the variation in the angular momentum, δJ , should be zero on average,

$$\delta J = 0. \tag{17}$$

This reasoning reveals that the angular momentum of a Kerr black hole containing a real graviton in the graviton condensate remains $J = 2\hbar$ in the mean-field approximation. Since a graviton does not have electric or magnetic charges, the Planck-sized Kerr black holes formed around gravitons also lack these charges. From these considerations, one learns that in the mean-field approximation, only the mass parameter can vary in the Kerr black hole containing a real graviton through the exchange of virtual gravitons. Therefore, we deduce that the mass parameter M of the Kerr black hole is the parameter of variation in the mean-field approximation.

An application of the no-hair theorem of black holes reveals that as a result of the influence of spacetime fluctuations through the exchange of virtual gravitons in the aggregated body, at least in the mean-field approximation, the geometry around a real graviton in the aggregated body remains that of the Kerr black hole. Only the mass parameter of this Kerr black hole can vary.

Utilizing mean-field analysis, we determine the order of the mass parameter of the Kerr black hole around a real graviton in the aggregated system of real gravitons. We use n to denote the number of nearest neighbors of a real graviton in the aggregated body of gravitons.

Since the spacing of gravitons in the aggregated body is d , an exchange of a virtual graviton occurs within the time frame

$$\Delta t \sim \frac{d}{c}. \tag{18}$$

Due to the energy–time uncertainty relation $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$, the exchanged energy in the process of the virtual graviton exchange is estimated as:

$$\Delta E \sim \frac{\hbar}{2\Delta t} \sim \frac{\hbar c}{2d}. \tag{19}$$

Because the number of nearest neighbors is n , the net amount of exchanged energy is estimated as:

$$n\Delta E \sim \frac{n\hbar c}{2d}. \tag{20}$$

This yields the order of energy associated with the spacetime fluctuation. We use \overline{M} to denote the mass parameter of the Planck-scale sized Kerr black hole formed around the real graviton in the mean-field approximation. Then, considering the mean-field approximation of the spacetime fluctuation, $\overline{M}c^2$ must be equal, on the order, to the energy fluctuation (20):

$$\overline{M}c^2 = \frac{n\hbar c}{2d}; \tag{21}$$

therefore, the order of \overline{M} is determined to take the following value:

$$\overline{M} = \frac{n\hbar}{2cd}. \tag{22}$$

As we just discussed, the angular momentum of the Kerr black hole confining a real graviton formed in the aggregated body of gravitons remains $2\hbar$. Thus, the previous discussion in Section 2.2 applies to this Kerr black hole. Due to the condition of the Kerr black hole forming a horizon, the mass parameter \overline{M} of this Kerr black hole has a lower bound of $\sqrt{2}m_P$:

$$\overline{M} = \frac{n\hbar}{2cd} \geq \sqrt{2}m_P. \quad (23)$$

Utilizing the fact that $\frac{\hbar}{cm_P}$ is identical to the Planck length l_P , from relation (23) one obtains the following upper bound on the spacing d of gravitons in the aggregated body:

$$\frac{n}{2\sqrt{2}}l_P \geq d. \quad (24)$$

Since the lower bound of the mass parameter \overline{M} already reached the Planck mass scale, \overline{M} must be on the order of the Planck mass. This observation implies that the spacing d of gravitons in the aggregated body is on the order of n times the Planck length l_P , or nl_P .

5 Remarks on the atomic structure and graviton condensate

A structure in which a graviton film, formed as a result of graviton condensation, confines a gas of quarks and gluons was discussed in [7]. Given this discussion, where the collision of two gold nuclei results in a gas of quarks and gluons confined within a graviton film—explaining the quark-gluon plasma produced in the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC)—a question naturally arises regarding the origin of the graviton condensate. Where does this graviton film come from?

Since the energy in gold ion collisions in the RHIC experiment is far below the energy scale of gravitons, it is unlikely that the graviton film confining the gas of quarks and gluons is produced during the collision process. The energy involved in the nuclei collision is much less than the energy required to generate gravitons. This argument implies that the graviton film is not formed at the time of collision; therefore, it must have existed prior to the nuclei collision. In other words, the remaining possibility is that the graviton films already existed around the nuclei of the gold ions before the collision.

Now suppose a situation where one atom has its nucleus confined within a graviton film and another atom does not (its nucleus is not confined within a graviton film). This raises the issue of atoms existing in different forms. For example, this implies the existence of one hydrogen atom possessing a graviton film as part of its internal structure and another hydrogen atom lacking this internal structure. This is physically inconsistent. Thus, the existence of an atom with a graviton film surrounding its nucleus implies that every atom contains a graviton film confining its nucleus.

This series of considerations applied to the model of quark-gluon plasma as a gas of quarks and gluons confined within a graviton film suggests that all atoms contain a graviton film as

part of their internal structure, and that the nucleus is confined within this film of graviton condensate.

However, an atom consists of a nucleus and electrons bound to the nucleus. Are these electrons also confined within the graviton film? If so, several issues arise. First, if there is one electron not confined within the graviton film and another electron confined within it, these two types of electrons would be observed as different particles³. Second, if the electrons in an atom were inside the graviton film, ionization of the atom would be very difficult to occur, which contradicts our observations. Furthermore, the idea of electrons existing inside the graviton film implies that the entire atomic structure (except for the graviton film) would be confined within it. If this were true, for example, considering metal atoms arranged to form a metal, the resulting metal would also be covered by a graviton film. There might then be a limitation on the size of the metal that the graviton film could cover, but for a sufficiently small piece of metal, this could occur, assuming the electrons in the atoms are within the graviton film. This would result in a liquid-like state for the metal with very low viscosity, which clearly does not describe the metals we observe. For instance, iron at room temperature is solid, not liquid-like. Therefore, the possibility that the electrons in an atom exist within the graviton film is ruled out.

These arguments lead us to the following hypothesis: **In an atom, there is always a graviton film surrounding the nucleus, but the electrons exist outside this film.** This provides a more precise description of the atom than the traditional picture, which consists merely of a nucleus and electrons bound to it.

Before concluding this section, it is worth making the following remark: The discussion we made earlier applies to a hydrogen atom. This implies that there is a film of graviton condensate surrounding the hydrogen atom's nucleus. However, in a hydrogen atom, the nucleus consists of a single proton. This suggests that a film of graviton condensate surrounds the proton. This can be closely related to the quark confinement problem. The fact that free quarks and gluons have never been observed may originate from the notion that a film of graviton condensate always confines quarks and gluons within it.

6 Concluding remarks

We demonstrated that when multiple real gravitons are present, the quantum gravitational effect of exchanging virtual gravitons among them leads to the instability of real gravitons, resulting in graviton condensation.

Using the mean-field approximation method applied to the graviton condensate, we estimated the spacing of real gravitons within the condensate. We showed that the spacing between real gravitons in the condensate has an upper bound on the order of the product of the Planck length l_P and the number of nearest neighbors.

We also discussed that the graviton condensation phenomenon, when applied to the model

³One may argue that an electron confined in a graviton film could be a muon. However, the muon decays with a short lifetime; therefore, an electron confined in a graviton film cannot be considered a muon.

of quark-gluon plasma proposed in [7], suggests that there is always a graviton film surrounding the atomic nucleus. In particular, when considering the hydrogen atom, since its nucleus is a proton, this suggests the existence of a graviton film surrounding the proton. Based on this observation, the graviton film may explain the confinement of quarks and gluons.

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